

Study on Factors Affecting Successful Outcome of Ultrasound Guided Hydrostatic Reduction of Ileocolic Intussusception in Children

M S N Chaturvedhi¹, Subrat Kumar Mohanty², Dharaneesh Ch³, Sudhansu Sekhar Mohanty⁴, Harish Chandra Tudu⁵, Varsha M T⁶

¹Post Graduate Trainee, Department of General Surgery, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

²Professor, Department of General Surgery, Mch Paediatric surgery Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

³Post Graduate Trainee, Department of General Surgery, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

⁴Associate professor, Department of Radiology, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

⁵Consultant, Department of Paediatric Surgery, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

⁶Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatric Surgery, Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. M S N Chaturvedhi

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Abstract

Objectives: The present study was to determine what all factors are responsible for favourable outcome of USG guided hydrostatic reduction of ileocolic intussusception.

Methods: Pre-warmed normal saline (warmed to body temperature, 36.5 - 37.5°C) was introduced via catheter into the rectum and proximal colon by hanging the bottle 120 cms above table height and allowing free flow under gravity. During the procedure, the retrograde movement of saline and the regress of intussusceptum were continuously monitored under real time ultrasound guidance. Besides, the peritoneal cavity was scanned intermittently in order to detect sudden increase in fluid and simultaneous depletion of fluid from the colon, suggesting bowel perforation. A maximum of 3 attempts were permitted, each attempt lasting 3 to 5 min with a gap of less than 3 min between the attempts. After failed third attempt, the procedure was ended without delay and the patient shifted urgently to the operation theatre for surgical reduction or resection with end- to-end bowel anastomosis. Patients who underwent successful USGHR were subsequently kept in the ward and observed for a minimum period of 24 hours to detect any complication.

Results: The mean age of the patients were 3.61 years. The highest proportion of cases been observed in male category (64.7%) followed by females (35.3%). USG guided hydrostatic reduction was attempted in 50 cases and not attempted in 1 case. USG guided hydrostatic reduction distribution which was successful with complete reduction in 1st sitting in 48 cases and partial reduction in 2 cases which were then taken up for the 2nd sitting and were completely reduced. Mean time taken for completion of the procedure was 04:23 minutes. Mean quantity of NS used during the procedure was 2.97 Litres.

Conclusions: Children who are diagnosed with intussusception early generally have a higher rate of effective hydrostatic reduction compared to those who are diagnosed later. Ultrasound- guided hydrostatic reduction is a highly effective and safe method for treating intussusception, making it the chosen initial treatment for suitable individuals. The success rate gained was exceedingly high.

Keywords: USG guided hydrostatic reduction, Ileocolic intussusception, Children.

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Introduction

The term "intussusception" describes how a portion of the intestine invaginates (telescopes) inside itself. It is the predominant abdominal emergency in early infancy, especially in children under the age of two [1].

Hutchinson documented the first successful surgical repair of intussusception in a newborn in 1871. In 1876, Hirschsprung [2] documented his use of enema as a therapy for intussusception [3].

This approach was correlated with an estimated death rate of 35 percent, which is much lower than

the mortality rates seen following surgical procedures. The technique of reducing intussusception via fluoroscopy-guided enema was first documented in 1927 [4] and quickly became a standard practice among radiologists. Furthermore, the approach has advanced to use ultrasound as an additional imaging modality. Historically, reduction was carried out by using barium or other liquid contrast agents, known as hydrostatic enema. However, it is also possible to do reduction using air or carbon dioxide, referred to as pneumatic enema.

Intussusception, a medical condition, was first documented by Barbette [5] in 1674. However, it wasn't until 1977 that the specific characteristics of this condition were defined by sonographic examination. Subsequent to that, several studies have used ultrasonography as a diagnostic tool for this illness, achieving an exceptionally high level of accuracy with a specificity and sensitivity of almost 100%.

The initial ultrasound-guided hydrostatic reduction (USGHR) with normal saline was performed by Kim [6] and his team in 1982. The use of sonography to guide the hydrostatic reduction of intussusception using tap water, regular saline, or Ringer's lactate solution has recently been accepted [7]. There are several benefits associated with USGHR of intussusception. Objectives of our study was to determine what all factors are responsible for favorable outcome of USG guided hydrostatic reduction of ileocolic intussusception.

Material and Methods

Study Population: Patients admitted in Department of General Surgery and Paediatric surgery with the diagnosis of ileocolic intussusception at KIMS, Bhubaneswar, Odisha for treatment, from JUNE 2022 to JULY 2024 were considered for this study.

Inclusion Criteria

- All the paediatric age group patients.
- Patients with confirmed diagnosis of ileocolic intussusception.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with acute intestinal obstruction
- Patient with signs and symptoms of peritonitis
- Patients with signs and symptoms of perforation
- Patients who refused for surgery
- Patients with gangrenous bowel
- Patients with sepsis and shock

Based on the number of patients admitted to the Dept. of General Surgery, KIMS and PBM Hospital, Bhubaneswar with ILEOCOLIC INTUSSUSCEPTION on evaluation by clinical, laboratory and imaging procedures who underwent surgery, the time frame dictates the estimated sample size to be around 25 cases per annum. So, the

sample size encountered during the study period around 50 cases. However, the scope of increasing / decreasing the number of cases exists depending upon the availability within the study period.

Study Setting: The study been conducted in the Dept. of General Surgery and paediatric surgery with assistance from the Dept. of Radio-Diagnosis in KIMS and PBM Hospital, Bhubaneswar, from JUNE 2022 to JULY 2024.

Method of Collection of Data: The patients, satisfying the inclusion criteria, after clinical, laboratory evaluation, were subjected to USG of Abdomen and Pelvis, and a report were obtained from the radiologist regarding the status of intussusception. The data were collected in a pretested Case Record Proforma designed for the study and been assessed by appropriate statistical methods.

Method of Follow-Up: The patients at the time of discharge been advised to review with previous reports at the Dept. of General Surgery and paediatric surgery, KIMS and PBM Hospital, Bhubaneswar during follow-up.

Procedure: Ultrasound scan of the patient was performed in the radiology department by the radiology senior resident with Ultrasound Machine using 10-15 MHz linear high frequency probe to validate the diagnosis of intussusception.

After ultra sonographic validation, the attending radiologist in collaboration with senior resident of paediatric surgery were performed USGHR. The surgical team comprising of the on-call paediatric surgeon, anaesthetist and peri-operative nurses were informed antecedent to the procedure to meet the eventuality of complications such as perforation and failed reduction that requires surgery.

The patient was kept in the supine position and a suitable sized Foley catheter (10F- 18F) was introduced into the rectum followed by balloon inflation.

The catheter size was chosen in accordance with the body size of the patient- 10F for infants, 14F for children aged 1-2 years and 16-18F for children older than 3 years.

The catheter bulb was inflated with 20-25 cc of normal saline (4-5 times its size) and then pulled back to the entrance of the anal canal to avert pericatheter fluid leakage.

It was then followed by bridging the gap between the two buttocks with the help of a band aid.

No sedation or premedication was administered to the patient. Pre-warmed normal saline (warmed to body temperature, 36.5 - 37.5°C) was introduced via catheter into the rectum and proximal colon by hanging the bottle 120 cms above table height and

allowing free flow under gravity. During the procedure, the retrograde movement of saline and the regress of intussusceptum were continuously monitored under real time ultrasound guidance. Besides, the peritoneal cavity was scanned intermittently in order to detect sudden increase in fluid and simultaneous depletion of fluid from the colon, suggesting bowel perforation. A maximum of 3 attempts were permitted, each attempt lasting 3 to 5 min with a gap of less than 3 min between the attempts. After failed third attempt, the procedure was ended without delay and the patient shifted urgently to the operation theatre for surgical reduction or resection with end- to-end bowel anastomosis. Patients who underwent successful USGHR were subsequently kept in the ward and observed for a minimum period of 24 hours to detect any complication.

Observations and Results

In the present study, the mean age of the patients were 3.61 years. The highest proportion of cases been observed in male category (64.7%) followed by females (35.3%). Vomiting distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have vomiting absent (90.2%). Abdominal pain distribution where the highest proportion of cases

been observed to have abdominal pain present (94.1%). Rectal bleeding pain distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have rectal bleeding pain absent (84.3%). Constipation distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have constipation absent (94.1%). Diarrhoea distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have diarrhoea absent (74.5%). Lymph node status distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have lymph node present (58.8%). Hyper echoic core distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have hyper echoic core present.

A-P diameter distribution where the calculated mean value been observed as 2.98. Length of intussusception distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have length of intussusception less than 3.5 (51.0%).

vascularity of bowel distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have vascularity of bowel present (98.0%). Abdominal distension distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have abdominal distension absent (86.3%).

Table 1: Shows The Length of Intussusception Distribution

Length of Intussusception	Frequency	Percent
Above Than 3.5	25	49.0
Less Than 3.5	26	51.0
Total	51	100.0

Table 2: Shows The Vascularity of Bowel Distribution

Vascularity of Bowel	Frequency	Percent
Absent	1	2.0
Present	50	98.0
Total	51	100.0

Fever distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have fever absent (84.3%). Abdominal pain duration for 12hrs to 3 days distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have abdominal pain duration for 1 day (60.8%) followed by 2 days (19.6%). USG guided hydrostatic reduction was attempted in 50 cases and not attempted in 1 case. USG guided

hydrostatic reduction distribution which was successful with complete reduction in 1st sitting in 48 cases and partial reduction in 2 cases which were then taken up for the 2nd sitting and were completely reduced. Mean time taken for completion of the procedure was 04:23 minutes. Mean quantity of NS used during the procedure was 2.97 Litres.

Table 3: Shows The Abdominal Distension Distribution

Abdominal Distension	Frequency	Percent
Absent	44	86.3
Present	7	13.7
Total	51	100.0

Figure 1: Shows The Fever Distribution

Table 4: Shows The Abdominal Pain Duration For 12hrs to 3 Days Distribution

Abdominal Pain Duration For 12hrs To 3 Days	Frequency	Percent
1 Day	31	60.8
2 Days	10	19.6
3 Days	7	13.7
Absent	3	5.9
Total	51	100.0

Table 5: Shows The Success Rate Distribution in USG Guided Hydrostatic Reduction

USG guided hydrostatic reduction		
Complete Reduction In 1 st Sitting	Complete Reduction In 2 nd Sitting	Total
48 Cases	2 Cases	50

Discussions

The present study entitled “Study on factors affecting successful outcome of USG guided hydrostatic reduction of ileocolic intussusception in children” after following strict inclusion and exclusion criteria took a total of 51 cases and the study analysis showed the age distribution where the mean age been calculated as 3.61 for the present study. The study conducted by Ocal et al. in 2014 [8] involved a sample size of 72 patients, comprising 44 males and 28 females. The age of the participants as analysed showed ranged from 5 to 132 months. All participants had been diagnosed with intussusception and received treatment. USG was administered to all cases upon initial presentation.

In the above context, the study conducted by Issa et al. in 2021 [9] revealed that the group that did not succeed in hydrostatic reduction had considerably higher values for weight, age, duration of symptoms, and length of the intussusceptum.

While the study conducted by Avci et al. in 2018 [10] did not find any significant differences between patients who had successful and failure reduction in terms of gender, age, and body weight.

The present study in terms of the gender distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed in male category (64.7%) followed by females (35.3%). In study, Khan et al., 2023 [11] reported that 58.7% of the sample consisted of males, while 41.3% were females which is in contrast to the present study findings. In the above setting, Chukwubuike et al., 2020 [12] conducted a study which revealed that 80% of the patients were male. The average age of the patients was 8 months.

The present study finds the vomiting distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have vomiting absent (90.2%). In this regard, a study conducted by John et al. in 2016 [13] has recorded that the combination of abdominal pain, vomiting, and the passing of red currant jelly stool occurred in just one third of the patients. In study by Emeka et al., 2021 [14] discovered that 15.6% of the patients exhibited respiratory infections, presenting symptoms such as nasal discharge and cough. Additionally, 12.5% of the patients experienced gastrointestinal infections,

which manifested as diarrhoea and vomiting. Furthermore, 3.1% of the patients showed evidence of both respiratory and intestinal infections.

The present study finds the abdominal pain distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have abdominal pain present initially (94.1%) but when abdominal pain duration for 12hrs to 3 days were analysed where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have abdominal pain duration for 1 day (60.8%) followed by 2 days (19.6%). Similar finding been observed by Fahiem-Ul-Hassan et al., 2020 [15] study showed 86% cases had abdominal pain present.

The study conducted by Govind et al. 2024 [16] found that the most prevalent symptoms were stomach discomfort (76.1%), vomiting (65.9%), abdominal distension (44.3%), blood in stools (35.2%), constipation (43.2%), and diarrhoea (34.1%). The present study with context to the rectal bleeding pain distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have rectal bleeding pain absent (84.3%).

The study conducted by Avci et al. 2018 [17] found that rectal bleeding was observed in 62% of the patients. In the context of this investigation, Columbani et al., 2012 [18] found that the main symptoms of intussusception are vomiting and abdominal pain. The most frequently observed clinical signs are rectal bleeding and the presence of a palpable mass on the right side of the belly.

The present study shows the constipation distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have constipation absent (94.1%). Rahim et al., 2018 [19] in their study findings found that the most prevalent symptoms observed were rectal bleeding (80%), abdominal discomfort (78%), vomiting (72%), and a palpable mass in the belly (70%). Abdominal distension was observed in 36% of the children, whereas constipation was reported in 26 children (52%).

The present study in terms of diarrhoea distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have diarrhoea absent (74.5%). In the study conducted by Digant et al., 2012 [20], in this context showed the most symptom was diarrhoea with bloody stool, reported by 80% of the participants. This was followed by cold and cough symptoms, reported by 40% of the participants, and abdominal pain, reported by 30% of the participants.

The present study shows the lymph node status distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have lymph node present (58.8%). The study conducted by Issa et al., 2021 [21] likewise found no significant correlation between sex, laboratory criteria, or mesenteric lymph node enlargement with the outcome of the reduction. In a study conducted by Digant et al., in 2012 [20], it was found that intussusceptions are the second most prevalent cause of acute intestinal blockages in children. Upon receiving a diagnosis, it is imperative

to initiate treatment promptly. While the precise causes are often unknown, several common elements that have been postulated as potential causes include swollen Payer's patches, enlarged lymph nodes, polyps, Meckel's diverticulum, and duplication cysts.,

The present study shows the A-P diameter distribution where the calculated mean value been observed as 2.98. Similarly for the length of intussusception distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have length of intussusception less than 3.5 (51.0%). The study conducted by Sun et al., 2022 [22] emphasised the potential utility of B- ultrasound examination in assessing the size of intussusception for effective management. This study further demonstrated that the diameter and length were significant factors that influenced the successful decrease. Their study found that out of the total number of children, specifically fifty-three, which accounts for 7.53% of the sample, experienced recurrent intussusception during a span of 4 years. Thirty-one occurrences, accounting for 3.40% of the total, were observed to have spontaneously decreased. The average diameter of intussusception was smaller in cases where reduction was effective compared to cases where reduction was unsuccessful.

The present study shows the lead point distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have lead point present (80.4%). In this context the study conducted by Banapour et al. 2015 [23] also discovered that the probability of a lead point being the underlying cause of ileocolic intussusception rises as children age.

The present study shows the vascularity of bowel distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have vascularity of bowel present (98.0%). Chandrasekharam et al., 2011 [24], and Bonnard et al., 2008 [25], conducted studies that confirmed intussusception as a prevalent cause of bowel obstruction in children.

The present study shows the abdominal distension distribution where the highest proportion of cases been observed to have abdominal distension absent (86.3%). Ocal et al., 2014 [8] study also observed the cases diagnosed with intussusception according to the full abdomen USG results, there was abdominal pain in 44 cases (61.1%), abdominal distension in 38 (52.8%), bloody stool in 30 (41.7%), vomiting in 11 (15.3%) and discomfort in 23 cases (31.9%) which is somewhat in similar lines to the present study findings.

The present study shows that the USG guided hydrostatic reduction was attempted in 50 cases (98%) and not attempted in 1 case (2%) due to compromised bowel vascularity in USG findings.

The present study shows that the USG guided hydrostatic reduction distribution which was successful with complete reduction in 1st sitting in 48 cases (96%) and partial reduction in 2 cases (4%) which were then taken up for the 2nd sitting and were completely reduced.

The present study shows that the meantime taken for completion of the procedure was 04:23 minutes.

The present study shows that the mean quantity of NS used during the procedure was 2.97 Litres.

The present study shows that 4 cases (8%) among the 50 cases had recurrence in 6 months after undergoing USG guided hydrostatic reduction.

The presence of factors such as diarrhoea, fluid in the peritoneal cavity, and emesis should not completely prevent the use of non-invasive treatments, it is crucial to acknowledge that they raise the likelihood of treatment failure. Surgeons must be ready to switch to surgery, if necessary, in such instances. If complications such as perforation, peritonitis, or the presence of pathologic lead points are excluded, paediatric surgeons should not be discouraged from attempting the reduction even if the symptoms have lasted for more than 24 hours. However, it is important to recognise that there is a larger probability of failure in such cases. Patients who have intussusception that extends to the rectum when they are admitted to the hospital need to be closely monitored because they have a higher chance of experiencing a recurrence while still in the hospital. Our study illuminates the influence of clinical symptoms that can be readily gathered within the initial minutes of an emergency care visit and offers significant understanding for making educated treatment choices. An effective method for a nonsurgical approach would involve first by the use of ultrasonography and physical examination. Additionally, if the patient's medical records and evaluation of clinical symptoms indicate a substantial presence of symptoms outlined in our study that necessitate cautious consideration, it is recommended to have a proficient paediatric surgeon available to perform the necessary surgery.

This study advises against making an immediate determination that surgery is required purely based on symptoms that have lasted for more than 24 hours.

Conclusions

Children who are diagnosed with intussusception early generally have a higher rate of effective hydrostatic reduction compared to those who are diagnosed later. As the length of intussusception is increasing there will be difficulty in reduction of intussusception. Ultrasound- guided hydrostatic reduction is a highly effective and safe method for treating intussusception, making it the chosen initial

treatment for suitable individuals. The success rate gained was exceedingly high.

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